

REPLACEMENT NAME

by

MASAO AZUMA

Rhizoconus nebulosus, sp. nov. Azuma, 1973 published in VENUS, the Japanese Journal of Malacology, Vol. 32, No. 2, pp. 34 & 37 (1973) *non nebulosus* Gmelin, 1791; *non nebulosus* Hwass in Bruguiere, 1792 which name being preoccupied, I propose *kiicumulus* nomen novum as replacement.

Rhizoconus kiicumulus, nom. nov. Azuma
Reproduction of holotype
measuring 40.5 mm x 21.5 mm preserved
in the Azuma Collection No. 16148